

FACULTY OF SCIENCES AND LETTERS

***THE INTERNATIONAL
CONFERENCE***

***"EUROPEAN INTEGRATION -
BETWEEN TRADITION AND
MODERNITY"***

EITM – 3rd Edition

22-23 OCTOBER 2009

TÂRGU - MUREŞ

ROMANIA

SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE

Presidents of Honour

Acad. Nicolae Manolescu (*Bucureşti* - România)

Prof.dr. Keith Hitchins (*Urbana* - SUA)

Presidents

Prof. dr. ing. Liviu Marian (*Tg. Mureş* - România)

Prof. dr. Ion Pop (*Cluj-Napoca* - România)

Members

Prof.dr. Harald Heppner (*Graz* - Austria)

Prof.dr. Alexandru Niculescu (*Udine* - Italia)

Prof.dr. Mircea Muthu (*Cluj - Napoca* - România)

Prof.dr. Gavrilă Neamtu (*Cluj - Napoca* - România)

Prof.dr. Virgil Stanciu (*Cluj - Napoca* - România)

Prof.dr. Francesco Miano (*Roma* - Italia)

Prof.dr. Antonio Spadaro (*Roma* - Italia)

Prof.dr. Luigi Alici (*Macerata* - Italia)

Prof.dr. Catherine Mayaux, (*Cergy –Pontoise* - Franţa)

Prof.dr. Rodica Pop (*Cluj - Napoca* - România)

Prof.dr. Cyrille Bertelle (*Paris* - Franţa)

Prof.dr. Kárady Viktor (*Budapesta* - Ungaria)

Prof.dr. Szögyi László (*Budapesta* - Ungaria)

Prof.dr. Anatol Petrenco (*Chişinău* - Moldova)

Prof.dr. Gheorghe Coman (*Cluj - Napoca* - România)

Prof.dr. Szigeti Jenő (*Miskolc* - Ungaria)

Prof.dr. Körtesi Péter (*Miskolc* - Ungaria)

Prof.dr. Militon Frenţiu (*Cluj - Napoca* - România)

Prof.dr. Florian Boian (*Cluj - Napoca* - România)

Prof.dr. Ion Tomescu (*Bucureşti* - România)

Prof.dr. László Pook (*Denver* - S.U.A.)

Prof.dr. Dan Dumitrescu (*Cluj - Napoca* - România)

The Conference is Organised in Partnership With:

THE MUREŞ COUNTY COUNCIL

THE TOWN HALL OF TÂRGU - MUREŞ

THE WRITERS' UNION OF ROMANIA

THE EUROPEAN ACTION ASSOCIATION

CONFERENCE PROGRAMME

Thursday, 22 October 2009

8³⁰-13³⁰ – Reception and registration of participants, Room R21

14⁰⁰ – **Official Opening**, Aula Magna

Opening Addresses

Dl. Marius PAȘCAN, Prefect of the Mureș County

Dr. Dorin FLOREA, Mayor of the Mureș County

Dna LOKODI Edita, Preșident of the Mureș County Council

Prof. dr. Liviu MARIAN, Rector of *Petru Maior* University

Prof. dr. Vasile BOLOȘ, Vice-rector of *Petru Maior* University

Prof. dr. Cornel SIGMIREAN, Chancelor of *Petru Maior* University

Prof. dr. Iulian BOLDEA, Dean of the Faculty of Sciences and Letters

Prof. dr. Nicolae BOCȘAN, Vice-rector of *Babeș Bolyai* University, Head of the Institute of Ecclesiastic Studies from Cluj-Napoca

16³⁰-17⁰⁰ – **Coffee Break**

17⁰⁰-19⁰⁰ – Opening of the International Symposium *Understanding Intelligent and Complex Systems* (coordonator: lecturer dr. Iantovics Barna)

19⁰⁰ – **Cocktail** - the Guest House from „Week-End” Complex

Friday, 23 October 2009

9⁰⁰-11⁰⁰ – Paper Presentations

11⁰⁰-11³⁰ – Coffee Break

11³⁰-13⁰⁰ – Paper Presentations

14⁰⁰ – Lunch Break

16⁰⁰-19³⁰ – Paper Presentations

20⁰⁰ – **Festive Dinner** - the Guest House from „Week-End” Complex

**THE MESSAGE OF THE RECTOR OF
PETRU MAIOR UNIVERSITY, TÂRGU- MUREȘ**

Dear guests,

The International Conference *European Integration –Between Tradition and Modernity* has become a tradition in the academic life of *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mures, bringing together within a generous range of topics scholars and researchers from different fields of tremendous importance for the contemporary society, a society that is supposed to secure its future not only on the economic and ecological level, but also on the spiritual one. Culture, fundamental sciences, literature and art gain new connections and dimensions through fundamental changes and structural progress, so that the social end-results of education and research become extremely important. We live in a society of knowledge, from which we benefit directly in our everyday life. Non scholae sed vitae discimus (We do not learn for the school, but for life) becomes a creed that every academic institution has to put into practice by means of its activities. The distance between education and research is very short, especially in academic systems. Research generates new knowledge, creates a favourable atmosphere for change, and provides people with information and data which help them to become aware of the mysteries of the universe and to make the most of their activity in all fields of knowledge. In this interesting and captivating century, to the noble mission of educating the younger generations we must also add the fruit of the efforts in research, materialized in interesting works and papers, together with ideas generated by the creative ability which ennobles the personality of the academic.

Petru Maior University of Târgu-Mures, the host of this particular event, is permanently changing and gaining new valences. Our specializations, assets, human resources and research grants are all in an upward dynamics, which proves that we are on the right track and also gives us the certainty of our continued existence as an institution with clearly defined and completely assumed missions. The International Conference *European Integration –Between Tradition and Modernity*, which is at its third edition, integrates into the tradition of far-reaching scientific events that have been taking place at our university throughout time. The fact that this conference is organized by the Faculty of Sciences and Letters of *Petru Maior* University proves once again how important it is for us to consolidate our cooperation with other universities and institutions of research from our country and from abroad.

I wish to express my hope that this scientific event will take place under the most favourable auspices and that it will represent a remarkable starting point for further evolution and development in the field of knowledge. Let this international conference provide a good opportunity for us to gain and transfer knowledge, to generate new theories in the world of science – essential aspirations of any contemporary research.

I wish this conference to be a complete success, and to all participants happiness, health and ‘good speed’!

**Prof. dr. Liviu MARIAN,
RECTOR**

October 23rd 2009

PAPERS PRESENTED IN SECTIONS

Session ROMANIAN LITERATURE (I) – Room R21

Moderators: Al. Cistelean - Prof. dr.

Andrei Bodiou - Prof. dr.

9⁰⁰-11⁰⁰

1. Andrei Bodiou, Prof. dr., *Transilvania University, Braşov, The artist and the politician: from innocence to pragmatism*
2. Cornel Moraru, Prof. dr., *Petru Maior University, Târgu-Mureş, Cioran and the Paradigm of European Nihilism*
3. Rodica Ilie, Assoc. Prof. dr., *Transilvania University, Braşov, The Project of European Literature in the 20th Century: Utopian Image and Historic Experience*
4. Adrian Lăcătuş, Assoc. Prof. dr., *Transilvania University, Braşov, Retractable Literature. Notes on Romanian Literature during Communism.*
5. Mariana Andrei, Assoc. Prof. dr., *University of Piteşti, The Theory of Travel between Knowledge and Anger (Marin Sorescu, Jurnal)*
6. Virgil Podoabă, Prof. dr., *Transilvania University, Braşov, Does Romanian Post-modernist Prose Exist?*

11⁰⁰-11³⁰ - Coffee Break11³⁰-13³⁰

1. Al. Cistelean, Prof. dr., *Petru Maior University Târgu-Mureş, Natalia, the Drug-Woman*
2. Caius Dobrescu, Prof. dr., *University of Bucharest, Ţiganiada - an Evergreen of European Liberal Luminism*
3. Eva Monica Szekely, Assoc. Prof. dr., *Petru Maior University Târgu-Mureş, Developing pragmatic competence through Literature, Film and Culture*
4. Cătălin Ghiţă, Lecturer dr., *University of Craiova, Scripts of Terror in Romanian 19th century prose*
5. Tiberiu Herdean, Dr., *Eötvös Loránd University of Budapest, The Intimate Journal in the Romanian Novel between the two World Wars*

13³⁰ – Coffee Break14⁰⁰ - 15³⁰ - Lunch Break16⁰⁰-19³⁰

1. Georgeta Moarcăş, Asistent dr., *Transilvania University of Braşov, Survivals of Expressionism in Ioan Es. Pop's Poetry*
2. Elena Agachi, Dr., *National College „A.T.Laurian”, Botoşani, Mircea Eliade: The Problematical aspect of Fantastic Literature*

3. Ruxandra Ivăncescu, Assoc. Prof. dr., *Transilvania University of Braşov, Historiographic Metafiction in Modern Romanian Literature*
4. Dorin Ştefănescu, Assoc. Prof. dr., *Petru Maior University of Târgu-Mureş, As Long as the Eye can See (Around a Poem by B. Fondane)*
5. Mihaela Stoenescu, Univ. Assist., University of Bucharest, *Historic Myth . Tradition and Modernity*

20⁰⁰ - Festive Dinner

Session ROMANIAN LITERATURE (2) – Room R04

Moderators: Mariana Neţ - Prof. dr.

Iulian Boldea - Prof. dr.

9⁰⁰-11⁰⁰

1. Mariana Neţ, Prof. dr., Institute of Linguistics „Iorgu Iordan – Al. Rosetti” Bucureşti, *Bucharest 1906. A portrait of the city as a grown-up*
2. Iulian Boldea, Prof. dr., *Petru Maior University of Târgu-Mureş, Identity and Discontinuance in E.M. Cioran’s Work*
3. Rodica Marian, Prof. dr., 1st degree researcher, Romanian Academy, Institute of Linguistics and Literary History „Sextil Puşcariu”, Cluj-Napoca, *Evening-Star’s “Blindness” and “the Ashes” in Eminescu’s Heart*
4. Lucian-Emil Roşca, Assoc. Prof. dr., Academy of Theatric Art, Târgu-Mureş, *Cultural Diversity and European Integration*
5. Dan Botezatu, Trainer, *Transilvania University of Braşov, Primo Levi: The Subject and the Testimony*

11-11³⁰- Coffee Break

11³⁰-13³⁰

1. Teodor Vidam, Prof. dr., Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, *The Place and Role of the Literary Language Compared with other Types of Languages*
2. Aliona Grati, Assoc. Prof. dr., Institute of Philology of Academy of Sciences of Moldova, *Dialogism – a Poetic Presentation Principle. Man and Social Reality in Moldavian Post-Soviet Literature*
3. Eugeniu Nistor, Lecturer dr., *Petru Maior University of Târgu-Mureş, Communication and Knowledge in Postmodernist View*
4. Dumitru Mircea Buda, Assistant, *Petru Maior University of Târgu-Mureş, The Rehabilitation of Prose in Romanian post-2000 literature – Themes and Languages*
5. Viorica-Ela Caraman, PhD. candidate, Researcher, Institute of Philology of Academy of Sciences of Moldova, *Poetic Personalization vs. De-personalization – an Inertial Paradox of Integration*
6. Maria Dorina Paşca, Lecturer dr., *Time from a psychological point of view in Blaga’s poetry*

14⁰⁰ - 15³⁰ - Lunch Break

Session ROMANIAN LITERATURE (3) –Room A412

Moderators: Dumitru-Mircea Buda - PhD. Candidate

Veronica Buta- PhD. Candidate

9⁰⁰-11⁰⁰

1. PhD. Candidate Anca Tomoioagă, University of Oradea, *The Psalmist and His God in Postmodernism (Șt. Augustin Doinaș's "Psalmi")*.
2. PhD. Candidate Ioana Laslo, Petru Maior University, Târgu-Mureș, *Erotic Avatars in Romanian Poetry (From Anton Pann to Emil Brumaru)*.
3. PhD. Candidate Nicoleta Laura Gabor, Petru Maior University, Târgu-Mureș, *Stylistic and Lexical Features in the Novel "Zabei Orbul" by Vasile Voiculescu*
4. PhD. Candidate Doina Stănescu, University of Bucharest, *Arghezi's Poetics - Tradition and Modernity*
5. PhD. Candidate Ana Capotă, Petru Maior University, Târgu-Mureș, *Mihail Sebastian – An Inter-war playwright*
6. PhD. Candidate Lucreția Bogdan, Petru Maior University, Târgu-Mureș, *The Archetypal Dimension of the Myth of Sacrifice*
7. PhD. Candidate Angela Șerdean, Petru Maior University, Târgu-Mureș, *Marin Preda's Journalism and Non-Fiction Works*
8. PhD. Candidate Veronica Buta, Petru Maior University, Târgu-Mureș, *The Ethics of Irony*
9. PhD. Candidate Maria Laura Rus, Petru Maior University, Târgu-Mureș, *The Character as a Mediator in Ion Creangă's Fantastic Universe*

11⁰⁰-11³⁰ - Coffee Break11³⁰-13³⁰

1. Ph.D. Candidate, Alina Simuț, Oradea University, *The relationship Between Translations and Original Literature in Romanian Romantic Prose*
2. PhD. Candidate Dan Tiberiu Lotoțchi, Petru Maior University, Târgu-Mureș, *Corporality, Text, Referent in the Writing of Gheorghe Crăciun*
3. PhD. Candidate Anca Maria Mănăilă, Petru Maior University, Târgu-Mureș, *Dionysiac and Apollonic in Carceral Diarism: Paul Goma and N. Steinhardt*
4. PhD. Candidate Călin Crăciun, Petru Maior University, Târgu-Mureș, *Balkanology and the Specificity of Romanian Literature*
5. PhD. Candidate Diana-Anca Nițulescu, Petru Maior University, Târgu-Mureș, *Symbolic Archetypes and Mythical Structures in the Works of Ștefan Bănuțescu*
6. PhD. Candidate Romana Colceriu, Petru Maior University, Târgu-Mureș, *Cultural Discourse vs. Literary Discourse. Cultural Models, Individuals and Discourses*
7. PhD. Candidate Mihaela Bîja, Petru Maior University, Târgu-Mureș, *Marin Preda or The Complete Representation of Love*
8. PhD. Candidate Ramona-Carla Farcaș, Petru Maior University, Târgu-Mureș, *A Writer of the 80s: Petru Cimpoșu*

IETM 3

9. PhD. Candidate Melinda Crăciun, *Petru Maior* University, Târgu-Mureș, *Ioana Em. Petrescu's Diary and the Paradigm of Feminin Writing*

13³⁰ – Coffee Break

14⁰⁰ - 15³⁰ - Lunch Break

16⁰⁰-19³⁰

1. PhD. Candidate Lia Faur, *Petru Maior* University, Târgu-Mureș, *Love and Misogynism in Camil Petrescu's Works*
2. PhD. Candidate Ionela Florina Iacob, *Babeș Bolyai* University, Cluj-Napoca, *The Theme the "Swallowing Monster" in Romanian Traditional Texts. The Snake*
3. PhD. Candidate György Géza Árpád, *Petru Maior* University, Târgu-Mureș, *Life and Death in Ady Endre's Poetics*
4. PhD. Candidate Elena-Elvira Moldovan, *Petru Maior* University, Târgu-Mureș, *Eros and Thanatos in Mircea Eliade's Domnișoara Christina*
5. PhD. Candidate Dumitru-Mircea Buda, *Petru Maior* University, Târgu-Mureș, *The Maternal Complex in Monica Lovinescu's Diaristic Writing*
6. PhD. Candidate Viorel Nistor, *Petru Maior* University, Târgu-Mureș, *Resistance through Culture in the Romanian Post-War Space*
7. PhD. Candidate Diana Cantacuz-Streza, *Petru Maior* University, Târgu-Mureș, *Emil Botta – the Twilight Vision*
8. PhD. Candidate Cristina Timar, *Petru Maior* University, Târgu-Mureș, *Everyday Existence and Metaphysics in Petru Cimpoesu's "Simon Liftnicul"*
9. PhD. Candidate Nagy Imola Katalin, *Petru Maior* University, Târgu-Mureș, *The Peasant between Love and Wealth from Ion to Turi Dani*

20⁰⁰ - Festive Dinner

Session ROMANIAN LANGUAGE - Room R39

Moderators: GG Neamțu - Prof. dr.

Luminița Chiorean - Assoc. Prof. dr.

9⁰⁰-11⁰⁰

1. GG Neamțu, Prof. dr., *Babeș-Bolyai* University of Cluj-Napoca, *Contributions to the theory and analysis of the binary syntagm*
2. Lucia Dărămuș, dr., Culture editor for the Pro Saeculo magazine, *Language as a Structuring Element of the European Thinking Pattern*
3. Vasile Bahnaru, Assoc. Prof. dr., researcher, Manager of the Institute of Philology, the Academy of Science of Moldavia, Chișinău, *Linguistic principles in lexicographic presentation of Romanian verb*

4. Silvia Pitiriciu, Assoc. Prof. dr., University of Craiova, *About the marks of European-jargon in the Romanian language*
5. Doina Butiurcă, Assoc. Prof. dr., *Petru Maior* University, Târgu-Mureş, *Greek-Latin foundation of medical terminology*
6. Valerica Sporiş, Lecturer dr., *Lucian Blaga* University of Sibiu, *The expressive value of folk etymology and word games*

11⁰⁰-11³⁰- Coffee Break

11³⁰-13³⁰

1. Inga Druţă, Sup. researcher dr., Manager of the Centre of Terminology of the Institute of Philology, Academy of Science of Moldavia, Chişinău, *Modalities of transferring knowledge in informational society through electronic terminological dictionaries*
2. Ioan Dănilă, Associate Prof. dr. University of Bacău, *Romanian Language in Linguistic Atlas of the Csango Speech Community from Romania* (MCNA)
3. Voica Radu, Lecturer dr., *Aurel Vlaicu* University of Arad, *The Terminologies and their Contribution to the Renewing of the Romanian Vocabulary. Some Aspects*
4. Ana Ene, Lecturer dr., *Transylvania* University of Braşov, *Contributions of the <<Transylvanian School>> to the conceptualizing of the types of discourse - the polemical discourse*
5. Simina Terian-Dan, PhD. Candidate, Assistant, *Lucian Blaga* University of Sibiu, *Preliminaries to a typology of Romanian textemes. An integralist point of view*

13³⁰ – Coffee Break

14⁰⁰ - 15³⁰ - Lunch Break

16⁰⁰-19³⁰

1. Maria Laura Rus, PhD. Candidate, Assistant, *Petru Maior* University of Targu-Mureş, *Povestea lui Harap-Alb by Ion Creangă: a semantic point of view*
2. Alina-Paula Nemţuţ, PhD. Candidate, Assistant, University of Oradea, *Interjection in Momentele și schițele by I.L. Caragiale*
3. Bianca Oana Han, PhD. Candidate, Assistant, *Petru Maior* University of Targu-Mureş, *Translation and context*
4. Ioan Dănilă, Assoc. Prof. dr, University of Bacău, *The Number "Three" - meaning and outreach. A Textological Approach*
5. Luminița Chiorean, Assoc. Prof. dr., *Petru Maior* University of Targu-Mureş, *On the Grammar of supplementary predicative object*

20⁰⁰ - Festive Dinner

Session GENDER STUDY – Room R04

Moderators: **Tatiana Iațcu - Assoc. Prof. dr.**

Dr. Paulette Delliros

16⁰⁰-19³⁰

1. Paulette Delliros, Dr., Institute of Museum Research, Australia, *Reframing the Gaze: European Orientalist Art in the Eyes of Turkish Women Artists*
2. Smaranda Ștefanovici, Assoc. Prof. dr., *Petru Maior* University of Târgu- Mureș, *Gender and Individualism in American Culture*
3. Andreea Năznean, *Unirea* National College of Târgu-Mureș, *The Status of Islamic and Romanian Women*
4. Corina David, *George Coșbuc* Gymnasium, Târgu-Mureș, *Tell Us A Story, Jeanette...*
5. Emilia Albu, Assoc. Prof. dr. & Alexandra Silvaș, Lecturer dr., *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureș, *Gender and Personality*
6. Conf.dr. Maria Georgescu, Universitatea „Petru Maior”, Tg. Mureș, *The Gender Problem in the Romanian Society*
7. Emilia Albu, Assoc. Prof. dr. & Lucica Emilia Coșa, Assistent, *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureș, *Sexual harrasing of the woman phenomenon of the contemporary society*
8. Cleminte Violeta, *Prezența femeilor în viața politică românească*

20⁰⁰ - Festive Dinner

Session ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND LIT'ERATURE – Room R34

Moderators: **Anișoara Pop - Lecturer dr.**

Adrian Năznean - Assistant

9⁰⁰ – 11⁰⁰

1. Sophia Frese, M.A., Ph.D. Candidate, Graduate School of North American Studies, John F. Kennedy Institute, Freie Universitaet Berlin, Germany - *“When was the last time we slept without dreaming we died? [...]” - Death and Violence in Palestinian- and Jewish-American Literature on the Middle East Conflict.*
2. Cătălin Ghiță, Assoc. Prof. dr., University of Craiova, *William Blake’s Concept of Imagination*
3. Nicoleta Petronela Apostol, Ph.D. Candidate, *Babeș-Bolyai* University, Cluj Napoca, *Veiled Identities*
4. Cristina Nicolae, Assistant, *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureș, *The Concept of Self in Virginia Woolf’s Mrs Dalloway.*

5. Corina Pușcaș, Assistant, *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureș, *The **Ghost Writer's** Generative Force and Momentousness in the Design of the Zuckerman Books by Philip Roth*
6. Doina David, *Dimitrie Cantemir* University of Târgu-Mureș, *Culture – process and phenomenon, synchronic and diachronic, particular and universal*
7. Ioana Stoica, PhD. Candidate, *Lucian Blaga* University of Sibiu, *Multiple Faces Of Reality In The Novel **Black Dogs** By Ian McEwan*
8. Iustin Sfariac, Lecturer dr., *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureș, *Annie Dillard and the Challenges of Ecocriticism*

11⁰⁰-11³⁰- Coffee Break

11³⁰-13³⁰

1. Anișoara Pop, Lecturer dr., *Dimitrie Cantemir* University of Târgu-Mureș, Romania, Susana Gómez Martínez, Lecturer dr., Faculty of Translation and Interpreting. University of Valladolid, Spain, *Making the Most of Blogs For Enhancing English Language Learning*
2. Rodica Ștefan, *Spiru Haret* University of Bucharest, *English as a Lingua Franca for Europe*
3. Bianca Oana Han, Assistant, *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureș, *Translation – a Form of Globalisation*
4. Daniela Dălălău, Assistant, *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureș, *The Use of Metaphors in Business Press Articles*
5. Claudia Leah, University of Oradea, *Some Influences of the English Linguistics upon the New Romanian Grammar*
6. Zoltán Ildikó Gy., Assistant, *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureș, *The semantics of slang*
7. Cristian Lako, Assistant, *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureș, *Translating for the Web*

13³⁰ – Coffee Break

14⁰⁰ - 15³⁰ - Lunch Break

16⁰⁰-19³⁰

1. Szűcs Eszter, Hungary, *Learning or acquiring?-Foreign language/English language knowledge of Hungarian employees in **Ireland***
2. Bradea Livia Otilia, Lecturer dr., *Babeș-Bolyai* University, Cluj Napoca, *Principles and Criteria Used in Teaching-Learning and Evaluation of Foreign Languages With Academic Students*
3. Adrian Năznean, Assistant, University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Târgu Mureș, *Aspects of Adult Language Learning*
4. Attila Imre, PhD., *Sapientia* University of Târgu-Mureș, *Metaphorical Expressions With the Romanian Peste*

5. Anișoara Pop, Lecturer dr., *Dimitrie Cantemir* University of Târgu-Mureș, *Collaboration and Networked Communities For Personal Development: Esp-Ro Yaboo group*
6. Claudia Leah, Lecturer dr., University of Oradea, *National Linguistic Identity In The Integration/ Globalization Context*
7. Tatiana Iațcu, Assoc. Prof. dr., *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureș, *The English Language and the Romanian Business Discourse*
8. Andreea Năznea, *Unirea* National College of Târgu-Mureș, *Task-Based Learning in Education*
9. Adrian Năznea, Assistant, University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Târgu Mureș, *Metacognition And Language Learning*

20⁰⁰ - Festive Dinner

Session FRENCH LANGUAGE AND LITTEATURE – Room R36

Moderators: **Liliana Alic - Assoc. Prof. dr.**
 Dr. Vladimir Florea

9⁰⁰-11⁰⁰

1. Diana Costea, Assistent dr., *Petrol-Gaze* University, Ploiești, *Encore- modifieur temporel, adverbe d'aspect et présuppositionnel. Le rôle de l'adverbe encore dans la séquence textuelle.*
2. Mihaela Neagu, Lecturer dr., *Transilvania* University, Brașov, *Les dictionnaires du français en tant qu'outils de langue*
3. Liliana Alic, Assoc. Prof. dr., *Transilvania* University, Brașov, *Le langage des médias: unité dans la diversité*
4. Georgiana Burbea, PhD. Candidate, Université de Picardie „Jules Verne”, Amiens, France, *Circuit énonciatif de quelques slogans publicitaires roumains et français*
5. Mihaela Popescu, Lecturer dr., *Transilvania* University, Brașov, *Gestion du corpus dans la recherche terminologique*
6. Marion Cohen-Vida, *Politehnica* University of Timișoara, *Vouvoiement ou tutoiement?*
7. Angelica Vâlcu, Maitre de conférences, Université *Dunarea de Jos*, Galați, *L'analyse de texte aux travaux dirigés en FLE. Une approche méthodique*
8. François Richerme, Centre Culturel Français, Attaché de coopération pour le français, drd. Eva Delcea, Centre Culturel Français, Chargée de mission Delf scolaire, *Le Cadre Européen Commun de Référence pour les langues : un outil d'apprentissage, d'enseignement et d'évaluation*
9. Pápai Réka Katalin, *Petru Maior* University of Târgu- Mureș, *Les problèmes pratiques de la traduction*

11⁰⁰-11³⁰ - Coffee Break11³⁰-13³⁰

1. Vladimir Florea, Dr., IUFM Versailles, *Dictatures et génocide: le devoir de mémoire dans la littérature de jeunesse*
2. Anca Clitan, PhD. Candidate, Babeş-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, *Le fantastique métamorphique de Corinna Bille*
3. Eva - Ildikó Delcea, Babeş-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, *L'entre-deux langues et la problématique identitaire chez Julien Green et Emil Cioran*
4. Roxana Ghiță, Lecturer dr., University of Craiova, *L'enfant, l'artiste et l'imagination poétique : les origines et l'évolution d'un mythe (depuis le romantisme allemand à Gaston Bachelard)*
5. Florica Mateoc, Assoc. Prof. dr., University of Oradea, *L'Europe et le monde d'aujourd'hui selon Amin Maalouf*
6. Alexandru Luca, Lecturer, Petru Maior University of Târgu- Mureş, *Les degrés de lecture du **Petit Prince** d'Antoine de Saint-Exupéry*

13³⁰ – Coffee Break14⁰⁰ - 15³⁰ - Lunch Break16⁰⁰-19³⁰

1. Cristian Stamatoiu, Assoc. Prof. dr., University of Theatric Arts, Târgu-Mureş, *Les trouvailles francophones des personnages « franco - aphones » de la comédie de Caragiale **Une nuit orangeuse***
2. Adriana Teodorescu, PhD. Candidate, Babeş-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, *La chambre ou comment extraire l'enfer de l'autre*
3. Corina Bozedeau, Assistent, Petru Maior University of Târgu- Mureş, *Minéralité et écriture dans l'œuvre d'Henry Bauchau*
4. Eugenia Enache, Assoc. Prof. dr., Petru Maior University of Târgu- Mureş, *Le tableau comme prétexte de roman : **Le Radeau de la Méduse***

20⁰⁰ - Festive Dinner

Session HISTORY – Room R33

Moderators: Dr. Szögi László
Cornel Sigmirean - Prof. dr.

9⁰⁰-11⁰⁰

1. Fábian István, Lecturer dr., *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureş, *Pax Romana and Ancient Europe*
2. Jean-François Dubost, Prof. dr., Université Paris 12 Val de Marne, *Société internationale des princes et circulations culturelles au temps de Marie de Médicis (1600-1642)*.
3. Kálmán Attila, Bolyai Highschool of Târgu-Mureş, *Transilvanian Aristocracy and Europe. The counts Haller*.
4. Gheorghe Bichicean, Prof. dr., *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureş, *Some Considerations Regarding of the French Revolution, Encyclopaedia and the Masonery*
5. Maria Dan, PhD. Candidate, Assistant, *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureş, *Defining identities. Romanians, Hungarians and Germans 1848-1849*
6. Varga Julia, Dr., *Romanian Students at the Gymnasium and Jesuite Academy of Cluj (1641-1773)*.
7. Cornel Sigmirean, Prof.dr., *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureş *The way towards Didactic Carreer in Austro-Hngarian Empire*
8. Szögi László, Dr., *Eötvös Loránd* University, Budapest, *Romanian Students at European Universities (1521-1918)*.

11⁰⁰-11³⁰ - Coffee Break

Moderators: Corina Teodor - Assoc.Prof. dr.
Jean François Dubost - Prof. dr.

11³⁰-13³⁰

1. Dénes Ilona, PhD. Candidate, CEU (Budapest), *Placing Central and South-Eastern Europe in the Missionary Schemes of 17th Century Catholicism*
2. Tóth Árpád, Assoc. Prof.dr, University of Miskolc (Hungary), *Voluntary society as a European cultural pattern. The spread and adaptation of a Western type of organisation in Central Europe in the 19th century*.
3. Corina Teodor, Assoc. Prof. dr., *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureş, *Feminine Horizons: Level of Instruction and Reading. Reflections on European Historiography During the last two Decades*
4. Laura Stanciu, Researcher dr., *1 Decembrie 1918* University of Alba Iulia, *Feminine Voices and Roles in the Romanian History of the Academic Medium (1990-2009)*
5. Radu Florian Bruja, Dr. *Ştefan cel Mare* University of Suceava, *The Activity of a Minister: Traian Brăileanu (septembrie 1940-ianuarie 1941)*.

6. Răzvan Pârâianu, Lecturer dr., *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureş, *The Romanian Intellectuals, the New Socialist Culture and the Communist Regime*,
7. Nina Tofan, PhD. Candidate, Republic of Moldova, Institute of History, State and Law of the Academy of Sciences of Moldova, *Culture as a Political Instrument in R.S.S.Moldovenească*
8. Inocențiu Dușa, PhD. Candidate, University of Theatre, Târgu Mureş, *The Identity Dynamic in the Euroepan Culture: The Drama of the Absurd*
9. Liviu Boar, PhD. director, National Archives – Mureş, *The Acces to Archives*

13³⁰ – Coffee Break

14⁰⁰ - 15³⁰ - Lunch Break

Moderators: Laurențiu Vlad - Prof. dr.

Dr. Berény Maria

16⁰⁰-19³⁰

1. Berény Maria, Dr., Institute of Research of Romanians, Hungary, *Life and Activity of Alexandru Mocioni*.
2. Emilia Martin, Dr., *A. Dürer* Museum, Gyula, Hungary, *The Apotropaic Role of Water in the Romanian Traditions from Hungary*
3. Elena Csobai, Dr., The County Museum of Békéscsaba, Hungary, *Romanian Communities from Gyula between the two World Wars*
4. Ana Borbély, Dr., Institute of Linguistics of the Hungarian Academy, *Bilingualime in Six Communities from Hungary*
5. Florea Ioncioaia, Dr., *Al. I. Cuza* University of Iași, *Against Bărnuțiu School . Power and Conflict at the Start of the University of Iași.*
6. Laurențiu Vlad, Prof. dr, University of București, *The English Political Model in the Romanian Conservatory Thought, the Cases of Apostol Arsache, Constantin Brăiloiu, Barbu Catargiu*
7. Ligia Cadeschi-Livada, Assoc. Prof. dr, University of București, *Marginals and Social Marginality. A Methodological Debate*
8. Leonidas Rados, Dr., *A.D.Xenopol* History Institute of Iași, *The Relationship Between the New School of History and Demosthene Russo*

20⁰⁰ - Festive Dinner

**Session INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS and
EUROPEAN STUDIES – Aula Magna**

Moderators: Michel Labori - Prof. dr.

Dr. Erol Kulahci

9⁰⁰-11⁰⁰

1. Győző Hajdics, Dr., Expert(MA) in International relations, Zalaegerszeg, Hungary, *The opportunity and difficulty of the development of the Common European Defence Policy after the Treaty of Lisbon*
2. Adrian Corpădean, PhD. Candidate, Babes-Bolyai University of Cluj-Napoca, *The Lisbon Treaty from the perspective of the 27 Member States*
3. Dragoș Păun, PhD. Candidate, Assistant, Babes-Bolyai University of Cluj-Napoca, *Euro-the Official Currency of Europe and of the Globalised World*
4. Miruna Baloșin, PhD. Candidate, Babes-Bolyai University of Cluj-Napoca, *The Analysis of Lobbying Structures in the UE*
5. Michel Labori, Dr., ex-Jean Monnet Professor, Lille, France, *Le bilan de l'intégration européenne et ses perspectives"*
6. Ioannis Panoussis, Dr., Maître de conférences à la Faculté Libre de Droit de Lille (ICL), France, Assesseur au Doyen chargé des Relations Internationales, *L'Union européenne et la gestion du risque terroriste (Quelques réflexions suite à l'arrêt Kadi du 3 septembre 2008)*
7. Dragoș Lucian Ciobanu, Advisor in the European Parliament, Bruxelles, *The creation of the European Area of Freedom, Security and Justice, in the debates of the EP*
8. Dumitru Costinean, PhD. Candidate, Ukraine, *The criteria for organizing regions in the EU and the implementation of that criteria.. A Comparative Approach*

11⁰⁰-11³⁰- Coffee Break

Moderators: Simion Costea - Assoc. Prof. dr.

Didier Blanc - Assoc. Prof. dr.

11³⁰-13³⁰

1. Ioana Leucea, PhD. Candidate, Assistant, Petru Maior University of Târgu-Mureș, *The Role of European Union in Promoting Human Security*
2. Lucian Săcălean, PhD. Candidate, Assistant, Petru Maior University of Târgu-Mureș, *Current Needs in the Process of Globalization*
3. Boloș Mihaela-Daciana, PhD. Candidate, Assistant and Boloș Brăduț Vasile, Lecturer dr., Petru Maior University of Târgu-Mureș, *Trademarks in Romania before and after joining the UE.*

4. Maria Costea, PhD. Candidate, researcher *Gh. Șincai* Institute of Târgu-Mureș, *The Implementation of the Treaty of Craiova*
5. Erol Kulahci, Dr., Researcher, Université Libre de Bruxelles, *L'Initiative pour l'emploi du Parti des socialistes européens*
6. Didier Blanc, Dr., Maître de conférences, vice-doyen, Université de Versailles, France, *La marche vers l'intégration européenne (1984-2009) : du projet de traité instituant l'Union Européenne (1984) au traité de Lisbonne*
7. Eric Olszak, Prof. dr., Université Catholique de Lille, France, *Les fondements économiques du développement durable*
8. Placide Mabaka, Dr., Maître de conférences - Université Catholique de Lille, France, *Le nouvel Statut du Depute european*

13³⁰ – Coffee Break

14⁰⁰ - 15³⁰ - Lunch Break

Moderators: Nicolae Păun - Prof. dr.

Dr. Giordano Altarozzi

16⁰⁰-19³⁰

1. Donila Pipa and Tiri Edfana, PhD. Candidates, Albania, *The European Perspective of the Western Balkans*
2. Simion Costea, Assoc. Prof.dr., *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureș, *The Eastern Partnership*
3. Tiberiu Tănase, Lecturer dr., National Intelligence Academy, Bucharest, *The Study of Intelligence in the Euro-Atlantic Area*
4. Nicolae Paun, Prof.dr., *Babes-Bolyai* University of Cluj-Napoca, *The European Project at the Moment of reality and challenges*
5. Mihaela Göndör, Assoc.Prof.dr., *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureș, *EU Fiscal Harmonization Policy vs. National Fiscal Systems*
6. Giordano Altarozzi, Dr., Sapiientia University of Rome, Italy, *Gli esuli romeni al Consiglio dell'Europa dell'Aja (maggio 1948)*
7. Sorlea Adrian, *Avram Iancu* High School of Târgu-Mureș, *The EU's Foreign Policy Towards Russia as Depicted in The European Parliament's Work.(2004-2008)*
8. Ioan Pogea, COREPER-EU – Bruxelles and Master – Maastricht University, *Lobbying Comitology: Interest Groups Participation in the Eco-Design Process.*
9. Delia Iliasa, European Parliament - Bruxelles, Master Université Libre de Bruxelles, *Le rôle du Parlement européen dans le processus décisionnel. Etude de cas: le parcours juridique de la Directive 65/2007/CE. Culture/Services*

20⁰⁰ – Festive dinner

**Session MATHEMATICS AND
INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY – Room R32**

**Moderators: Adrian Petrescu - Assoc. Prof. dr.
 Marcel Bogdan - Lecturer dr.**

9⁰⁰-11⁰⁰

1. Domenico Consoli, Universita Politecnica delle Marche, Ancona, Italy, *Textual Emotions Recognition With an Intelligent Software of Sentiment Analysis*
2. R.Y. Denis, S.N. Singh and S.P. Singh, University of Gorakhpur, India, *Representations of Positive Integers as Sum of Squares and Triangular Numbers*
3. Dumitru Rădoiu, dr., Assoc. prof. dr., *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureș, *Research Areas in Semantic Technology*
4. Adrian Petrescu, Assoc. prof. dr., *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureș, *Direct Decompositions of Quasigroups and Homotopies*
5. Marcel Bogdan, Lecturer dr., *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureș, *Generated Mosco convergence for sets*
6. Oprea Nicola, Assistant, *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureș, *Application of Extrapolation Method to Initial Value Problems in Ordinary Differential Equations*
7. Bogdan Crainicu, Assistant, *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureș, *Some Aspects on RC4 Distinguishing Attack*
8. Diana Mărginean Petrovai, Lecturer, *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureș, *Property of Regular Excessive Measures*

11⁰⁰-11³⁰ - Coffee Break

**Moderators: Dumitru Rădoiu - Assoc. Prof. dr.
 Ion Cozac - Lecturer dr.**

11³⁰-13³⁰

1. Călin Enăchescu, Prof.dr., *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureș, *Mathematical Aspects of Supervised Learning in Neural Computations*
2. Ion Cozac, Lecturer dr., *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureș, *A Webserver Architecture for the Timetable Problem*
3. Lefkovits Szidonia, PhD. Candidate, Assistant, *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureș, *Teaching Improvements on Haar Based Classifiers*
4. Barna Iantovics, Lecturer dr., *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureș, Florin F. Nichita, "Simion Stoilow" Institute of the Romanian Academy, Romania, David

IETM 3

Hobby, State University of New York at New Paltz, USA, *Knowledge-Based Mobile Agents*

5. Ioan Ispas, PhD. candidate, Assistant, *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureş, *On the Difficulty of the Image Recognition Problem*
6. Diana Mărginean, Lecturer dr. and Oprea Nicola Assistant, *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureş, *Properties of Potentials*
7. Finta Béla, Assoc.prof.dr., *Petru Maior* University of Târgu-Mureş, *Overdeterminate Infinite Liniar Systems*

20⁰⁰ - Festive Dinner

**PETRU MAIOR UNIVERSITY OF TÂRGU-MUREŞ HEREBY PRESENTS
ITS THANKS TO ALL THE INSTITUTIONS THAT HAVE
CONTRIBUTED TO THE SUCCESSFUL PROCEEDINGS OF OUR
INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
*EUROPEAN INTEGRATION – BETWEEN TRADITION AND
MODERNITY (IETM) – 3rd EDITION – 2009:***

- Mureş County Council
- Târgu-Mureş Town Hall
- The Writers' Union of Romania
- The *Vatra* Journal
- The *European Action* Association
- Continental Hotels